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Germinal epimutation of Fragile Histidine Triad (FHIT) gene is associated with progression to acute and chronic adult T-cell leukemia diseases

[Marcia Bellon](#),¹ [Izabela Bialuk](#),² [Veronica Galli](#),² [Xue-Tao Bai](#),³ [Lourdes Farre](#),⁴ [Achilea Bittencourt](#),⁵ [Ambroise Marçais](#),⁶ [Michael N. Petrus](#),⁷ [Lee Ratner](#),⁸ [Thomas A. Waldmann](#),⁷ [Vahid Asnafi](#),⁹ [Antoine Gessain](#),^{10,11} [Masao Matsuoka](#),^{12,13} [Genoveffa Franchini](#),² [Olivier Hermine](#),⁶ [Toshiki Watanabe](#),¹⁴ and [Christophe Nicolet](#)¹¹

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Human T cell Leukemia virus type 1 (HTLV-I) is etiologically linked to adult T cell leukemia/lymphoma (ATL) and an inflammatory neurodegenerative disease called HTLV-I-associated myelopathy or tropical spastic paraparesis (HAM/TSP). The exact genetic or epigenetic events and/or environmental factors that influence the development of ATL, or HAM/TSP diseases are largely unknown. The tumor suppressor gene, Fragile Histidine Triad Diadenosine Triphosphatase (FHIT), is frequently lost in cancer through epigenetic modifications and/or deletion. FHIT is a tumor suppressor acting as genome caretaker by regulating cellular DNA repair. Indeed, FHIT loss leads to replicative stress and accumulation of double DNA strand breaks. Therefore, loss of FHIT expression plays a key role in cellular transformation.

Methods

Here, we studied over 400 samples from HTLV-I-infected individuals with ATL, TSP/HAM, or asymptomatic carriers (AC) for FHIT loss and expression. We examined the epigenetic status of FHIT through methylation specific PCR and bisulfite sequencing; and correlated these results to FHIT expression in patient samples.

Results

We found that epigenetic alteration of FHIT is specifically found in chronic and acute ATL but is absent in asymptomatic HTLV-I carriers and TSP/HAM patients' samples. Furthermore, the extent of FHIT methylation in ATL patients was quantitatively comparable in virus-infected and virus non-infected cells. We also found that longitudinal HTLV-I carriers that progressed to smoldering ATL and descendants of ATL patients harbor FHIT methylation.

Conclusions

These results suggest that germinal epigenetic mutation of FHIT represents a preexisting mark predisposing to the development of ATL diseases. These findings have important clinical implications as patients with acute ATL are rarely cured. Our study suggests an alternative strategy to the current "wait and see approach" in that early screening of HTLV-I-infected individuals for germinal epimutation of FHIT and early treatment may offer significant clinical benefits.

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at [10.1186/s12943-021-01370-2](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12943-021-01370-2).

Keywords: HTLV-1, FHIT, ATL, ATLL, TSP, Leukemia, Lymphoma, Epigenetic, Methylation, Tax, TSP/HAM HAM, Cancer, Epimutation

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Background

Human T cell Leukemia virus type 1 (HTLV-I) is etiologically linked to adult T cell leukemia/lymphoma (ATL) and an inflammatory neurodegenerative disease called HTLV-I-associated myelopathy or tropical spastic paraparesis (HAM/TSP). The exact genetic or epigenetic events and/or environmental factors that influence the development of ATL, or HAM/TSP diseases are largely unknown. The tumor suppressor gene, Fragile Histidine Triad Diadenosine Triphosphatase (FHIT), is frequently lost in cancer through epigenetic modifications and/or

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Figure 3. From: Association of the promoter methylation and protein expression of Fragile Histidine Triad (FHIT) gene with the progression of differentiated thyroid carcinoma.

FHIT gene promoter methylation and its protein expression in DTC and NEC. FHIT gene promoter methylation and its protein expression were shown in DTC (n=65) and NEC (n=65). **, p < 0.01, as compared between DTC and NEC. Methylation: FHIT gene promoter methylation determined by PCR-based methylation analysis; Expression: FHIT proteins expression determined by IHC staining.

De-Tao Yin, et al. Int J Clin Exp Pathol. 2010;3(5):482-491.

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2.

Figure 1. From: Loss of FHIT Expression in Transitional Cell Carcinoma of the Urinary Bladder.

The *FHIT* gene. **A:** *FHIT* exons 1–10, STSs markers analyzed by PCR (1–10), and the five BACs covering the central portion of the *FHIT* gene. **B:** Homozygous deletions of the *FHIT* gene observed in SW780, CRL7930, and CRL7833 cells.

Raffaele Baffa, et al. Am J Pathol. 2000 Feb;156(2):419-424.

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3.

Fig. 1. FANCD2 depletion induces CFS gene expression.. From: FANCD2 modulates the mitochondrial stress response to prevent common fragile site instability.

a mRNA levels of large CFS genes measured by RT-qPCR after siFANCD2 transfection, compared to levels after siLacZ transfection. n = 5 (FHIT, WWOX, IMMP2L, PARK2), n = 3 (PTPRG) independent experiments. **p = 0.0011 (FHIT), ****p < 0.0001, ***p = 0.0009, **p = 0.0067 (PARK2). **b** Frequency of FRA3B and FRA6E breakage presented as the percentage of chromosome 3 and chromosome 6 homologs, with breaks at FRA3B and FRA6E, respectively. n = 4 and n = 3 independent experiments for FRA3B and FRA6E breakage, respectively. **p = 0.0064, *p = 0.0377. **c** Left, example of

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